

The logo for ICCM24, with 'ICCM' in dark blue and '24' in a lighter blue. The background of the slide features a city skyline on the left and a geometric pattern of triangles on the right.

ICCM24

24TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS

August 4-8, 2025 Baltimore Convention
Center - Baltimore, MD

Additive Manufacturing of Complex & Oscillating POSS-based 4D Structures

Nicole Gorohovsky, Ronen Verker, Noa Lachman

Composite Structures & Interfaces (SCI) Lab

Tel Aviv University

What are Bilayer Actuators?

Shape change due to external stimuli (temperature, humidity, etc.).

Bilayers: two polymeric layers with different CTEs.

Applications: actuators, sensors, soft robotics, & more.

Motivation

Traditional manufacturing limits design complexity & efficiency.

3D printing allows precise & complex shapes.

<https://lightandladder.com/>

<https://aspectbiosystems.com/>

Research Objectives

01

Develop a Direct Ink Writing (DIW) process for high-performance bilayer actuators.

02

Key focus: material adhesion, rheological control, & layer uniformity.

03

Improve scalability, precision, & reproducibility.

System Set Up

Materials

PolyPOSS – active layer

$x \approx 2.5$

Jeffamine D-230

**Polyhedral
oligomeric
silsesquioxanes
(POSS)**

Kapton film – passive layer

Gelation Time & Rheology

Rheometer

- Inflection point = gelation time

Preliminary Print

Single line printing

- Result:
 - poor polyPOSS/Kapton wettability
 - many de-wetting points → polyPOSS is absent.
- Solution: increase vol. flow rate & surfactant addition.

Printing Quality Optimization: 1D

A printing index (P_i) was developed
→ optimization of printing
parameters:

$$P_i = \frac{stdv}{avg}(w) \cdot \frac{stdv}{avg}(t) \cdot (\#_{dwp} + 1)$$

Printing Quality Optimization: 1D (Cont.)

Printing Quality Optimization: 2D

2D optimization: effect
of line-overlap %

Printing Quality Optimization: 3D

3D optimization: effect of 2nd layer vol. flow rate

Final Printing Achievements

- Material-substrate adhesion successfully controlled.
- Optimized DIW parameters → AMed reproducible, high-quality X-finger gripping bilayer actuators.

X-Finger Actuators

“Spider” Actuator

Conclusions & Future Aspirations

Key achievements:

- Printing optimization process.
- DIW-based high performance bilayer actuators.

Future work:

- Mechanical properties.
- New material formulations.
- Downscaling.

Mechanical properties

Effect of CNT addition on shape memory properties

Nozzle diameter effects

The Team

Special thanks to:

- **Dr. Noa Lachman**
- **Dr. Ronen Verker**
- Mr. Baruch Meirovich
- Mr. Arkadi Refalovich
- ADAMA center at Tel Aviv University
- CSI Lab members

The logo for ICCM 24 features the text 'ICCM' in a bold, dark blue sans-serif font, followed by '24' in a lighter blue sans-serif font. The background of the top banner shows a city skyline on the left and a geometric pattern of white triangles on a light blue background on the right.

ICCM24

24TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS

August 4-8, 2025 Baltimore Convention
Center - Baltimore, MD

QUESTIONS?